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(p. 122) One of the most renowned and critically acclaimed gay fiction writers of contemporary Ireland, Keith Ridgway emerged in the 1990s as a powerful and innovative literary voice concerned with the rapid changes taking place in Irish society.¹ Both Ridgway's 2001 story "Angelo," which appeared in his collection *Standard Time* (awarded the prestigious Rooney Prize for Irish Literature in 2001) and his novel *The Parts* (2003) foreground the injustice, alienation, and social divides of Celtic Tiger Dublin. In a 2012 interview, Ridgway remarks that in those years, Dublin "became a parody of gross commercialism and consumerism."² His fiction is highly critical of the neoliberal ethos of Celtic Tiger Ireland. Katherine O'Donnell notes that, even though the poor in *The Parts* "are occluded in the noise of the economic boom [and] repressed from the dominant social imaginery," they nonetheless "haunt the text."³ Despite his profound social critique, Ridgway does not succumb to a moralistic treatment of his subject matter, opting instead for a compelling use of black comedy and sarcasm. In terms of style and content, Ridgway's fiction also becomes representative of a contemporary trend in Irish literature, with authors who typically deal with socially silenced topics and identities. "Much Irish Literature," according to a recent article, "has moved away from dominant discourses and found an alternative strategy of representation that incorporates silence as a discursive tool in its own right."⁴ Silence, as Robin Patric Clair has theorized, is embedded in (p. 123) language, as "creating and re-creating our social realities" through the "organizing" of knowledge.⁵

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² Sinéad Gleeson, "'I Write Because I Don't Quite Know How To Live': Interview with Keith Ridgway," *Irish Times*, 14 July 2012.

³ Katherine O'Donnell, "The Parts: Whiskey, Tea, and Sympathy," in *Literary Visions of Multicultural Ireland: The Immigrant in Contemporary Irish Literature*, ed. Pilar Villar-Argáiz (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2013), 191.

⁴ Maria Beville and Sara Dybris McQuaid, "Speaking of Silence: Comments from an Irish Studies Perspective," *Nordic Irish Studies* 11, 2 (2009), 7.

⁵ Robin Patric Clair, *Organizing Silence: A World of Possibilities* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1998), 21.

Although there is ample historical evidence that male prostitutes have existed “since the time of the Romans and Greeks up through Victorian England and to the present,” prostitution is most often gendered as a female occupation.⁶ The feminization of the “world’s oldest profession” in patriarchal societies has clear implications regarding the nonrecognition of male prostitution and the perceived inferiority of prostitutes in general. In the case of “rent boys”—the type of male prostitute Ridgway represents in his fiction—their situation of inferiority typically arises from their social class, disadvantaged personal and familial backgrounds, and their very young age. In 1990s and early 2000s Ireland, in which Ridgway’s texts are set, meaningful public discussions of male prostitution were virtually nonexistent—which, for that matter, also appears to be the case today.⁷ Those few journalists who did comment on the existence of rent boy generally focused on matters other than class oppression or the boys’ experiences of marginalization. In 1994, a government minister was found in Dublin’s Phoenix Park in the company of a rent boy, but the media coverage highlighted only the politician’s tarnished reputation and his claim that he did not know that the boy was a prostitute: “He said he deeply regretted the distress the incident had caused to his wife and family.”⁸ Another 1994 article reported a politician’s dismay that the “law was not being stringently enforced” in the Phoenix Park, where young men were seen to offer their sexual service (the 1993 Sexual Offences Act made it illegal to solicit or loiter on the street for the purposes of prostitution). A few years later in Dundalk, the residents of a neighborhood urged the police to eradicate the uncomfortable presence of “teenage boys soliciting along the street” and adult men “picking up [these] youngsters for sex.”⁹ None of the press coverage considered the harsh personal conditions that may drive teenagers into prostitution; it is hard not to conclude that, for many people, the most pressing concern was not to help these boys out of prostitution, but to keep their trade out of sight.

(p. 124) A 1997 article in the *Irish Times* did give a glimpse into the ugliest side of this underworld, after a middle-aged man had slept with a rent boy and found him dead in bed beside him the following morning. The boy’s death was caused by “a combination of alcohol and drug abuse,” and the story reported that he came from “a dysfunctional family.”¹⁰ However terse the reportage, the fact remains that the boy hailed from an unfortunate background and that social services had failed to protect the minor’s welfare. In *Rent: The Secret World of Male Prostitution in Dublin* (2000), Evanna Kearins observes

⁶ David S. Bimbi, “Male Prostitution: Pathology, Paradigms and Progress in Research,” *Journal of Homosexuality* 53, 1–2 (2007), 8.

⁷ A study conducted between 2009 and 2012 found that “in Ireland, academic policy and advocacy research have tended to focus almost exclusively on female sex work.” This study also confirms a lower preponderance of street-based sex work today, due to the development of the internet and mobile phone applications (371). See P. J. Maginn and G. Ellison, “Male Sex Work in the Irish Republic and Northern Ireland,” in *Male Sex Work and Society*, ed. V. Minichiello and J. Scott (New York: Harrington Park Press, 2014), 370–71.

⁸ Alan Murdoch, “Irish Minister Set to Survive Scandal,” *Independent*, 9 March 1994.

⁹ Elaine Keogh, “Gardai Identify Men Linked with ‘Rent Boy’ Ring,” *Independent*, 11 September 1998.

¹⁰ Richard Balls, “Man Awoke To Find Teenage Rent Boy Dead in Bed Beside Him,” *Irish Times*, 12 April 1997.

that “the most common reasons for involvement in male prostitution included lack of money, homelessness (poverty), unemployment, drugs/alcohol abuse, poor family background/ abuse, sexual or physical abuse, desire for attention/companionship, sex or a combination of these factors.”¹¹ According to Kearins, there is a “perceived growth in male prostitution in Dublin,” but “little public concern has been expressed about it” due to the “lack of recognition of this subculture.”¹² Rent boys themselves are aware that their trade is socially unacceptable. Most of them are “are unwilling to admit involvement in prostitution for fear of legal and social recrimination.”¹³ Kearins insists on the need to implement policies to help these severely disadvantaged youngsters (many of them minors) out of prostitution, and decries “an absence of national policy on male prostitution.”¹⁴

For some of the commentators on Kearins’s book, her finding that heterosexually married men counted as the rent boys’ most common clientele became the most salient issue. In her review, Kathryn Holmquist offered the opinion these married men “suppress their true sexuality at great psychological cost,” and that, “when it all becomes too much to contain, they seek a brief sexual encounter with a male prostitute.”¹⁵ That the so-called “punters” tend to lead double lives seems true, but the notion that most of them are repressed homosexuals, or bisexuals, is debatable. There is ample evidence that some heterosexual men occasionally engage in gay sex, with no inner conflict as regards their sexual identity. As we also learn in Kearins’s book and in Liam McGrath’s short documentary *Boys for Rent* (1993), these clients have ephebophilic desires. They want to fulfill their most hidden sexual fantasies specifically with teenage (**p. 125**) boys, and not with adult men. A rent boy in McGrath’s documentary relates that teenagers as young as twelve entered prostitution, but “when you reach the age of twenty, you’re too old for [punters].”¹⁶ Another rent boy, interviewed by Kearins, tells us that “punters they do like ’em a bit young and all so I do often pretend I’m only sixteen.”¹⁷ In a review in *IrishHealth.com*, Jim Clarke, like Holmquist, assumes that those married men having sex with teenage boys are actually closeted gays, and thus calls male prostitution “a potent combination of homosexuality, vice, abuse and shame.”¹⁸ Both Holmquist and Clarke

¹¹ Evanna Kearins, *Rent: The Secret World of Male Prostitution in Dublin* (Dublin: Marino Books, 2000), 27.

¹² Kearins, 20.

¹³ Kearins, 122.

¹⁴ Kearins, 166.

¹⁵ Kathryn Holmquist, “‘Married guys, all they want is to touch and feel another guy’: Kathryn Holmquist Meets the Author of a New Study of this Invisible Subculture,” *Irish Times*, 15 March 2000, 13.

¹⁶ Liam McGrath, *Boys for Rent*, 1993. The documentary can be viewed in its entirety at <https://vimeo.com/116162119>

¹⁷ Kearins, 45.

¹⁸ Jim Clarke, “Male Prostitution and Health,” *IrishHealth.com*, 2018. <http://www.irishhealth.com/article.html?id=3387>.

confuse homosexuality (a sexual orientation) with ephebiphilia (a sexual preference).¹⁹ Their texts divert attention from the violence that ephebiphilia—in the form of exploitative sex—may involve. Moreover, they misleadingly suggest that punters have no other choice but rent boys to give expression to their allegedly secret homosexual orientation.

Whether or not punters are gay is of little relevance to the plight of the rent boys themselves. In fact, these responses to Kearins's book only illustrate how, as has happened in many other cultural contexts, "the narratives which surround male street prostitutes often are only peripherally related to the experiences and concerns of the sex workers."²⁰ What needs to be addressed is the sexual exploitation, social class oppression, and marginalization surrounding prostitution whether practiced by men or women, boys or girls. Recent studies have reiterated previous findings that most Dublin rent boys are undereducated and come from very difficult familial environments. A study in the *Journal of Homosexuality* found that among rent boys, the "average age for leaving school was 14 years, just below the legal age of 15... [Most] participants left home (p. 126) before they were aged 18. This was mainly because of stealing, drug use, or sexual or physical violence."²¹ There are also high levels of anxiety and depression among Dublin rent boys, for whom their work becomes "emotionally difficult" because of the fear and insecurity they experience.²² These studies insist on the need to tackle prostitution by focusing on the socio-economic and psychological worlds of the rent boys themselves—and not on married clients or their sexual orientation. In his fiction, Ridgway in no way adopts moralistic views on sexual identities and illicit sex. Rather, he foregrounds the unpalatable realities affecting rent boys, against a background of silence and nonrecognition.

Nonetheless, as Ridgway contrasts the experiences of male prostitutes with those of middle-class young men in both "Angelo" and *The Parts*, any consideration of his work needs to engage with the topic of gay identity in Celtic Tiger Ireland. Diarmaid Ferriter

¹⁹ I draw here on Joe Kort's definitions of sexual orientation and sexual preference. He uses such distinction when explaining the differences between homosexual men and the so-called SMSM (Straight Men who have Sex with Men): "A gay man's sexual orientation is characterized by lasting aesthetic attraction to, romantic love of, and sexual attraction almost exclusively towards those of the same gender. In contrast, SMSM might fantasize about men, but their primary sexual and romantic attractions are toward women. They are heterosexual men who for a variety of reasons engage in sexual behavior with other men... In understanding SMSM, a significant distinction is that between sexual preference and sexual identity. Sexual preferences are about various desires, positions, and fantasies one might have, whereas sexual identity is about how one self-identifies in terms of straight, gay, or bisexual." See Joe Kort, "Straight Men Who Have Sex With Men (SMSM)," GLBTQ online Encyclopedia. 2008. http://www.glbtqarchive.com/ssh/straight_men_who_S.pdf

²⁰ Kerwin Kaye, "Sex and the Unspoken in Male Street Prostitution," *Journal of Homosexuality* 53, 1–2 (2007), 40.

²¹ I. Mc Cabe, M. Acree, F. O'Mahony, J. McCabe, J. Kenny, J. Twyford, K. Quigley, and E. McGlanaghy, "Male Street Prostitution in Dublin: A Psychological Analysis," *Journal of Homosexuality* 58, 8 (2011), 1008.

²² I. Mc Cabe, R. Mills, D. Murphy, S. J. Winders, J. Hayden, D. Reynolds, J. McCabe, and A. McQuaid, "A Psychocultural Comparison of Male Street Prostitutes in Dublin and San Francisco," *Irish Journal of Psychology* 35, 2–3 (2014), 101.

argues that, due to the political and ideological dominance of the Irish Catholic church until the early 1990s, “a sexual liberalism based on individual rights experienced elsewhere in the West in the 1960s and 1970s was delayed in coming to Ireland.”²³ This culture of “sexual liberalism” became identified with the advent of the neoliberal policies of the Celtic Tiger economy. Public discourse during the economic boom “emphasised certain features and elided others”; despite the growing inequality in access to housing, education, and health care, the Celtic Tiger evoked “an euphoric sense of self-congratulation.”²⁴ The widening gap between the rich and the poor was conveniently silenced by a discourse of social justice that concentrated on the equality of social identities: for example, the increased visibility, recognition and protection of gay identity. According to Michael G. Cronin, the representations of gay men in Celtic Tiger Ireland promoted a notion of social progress that was connected with the lifestyle principles of liberal capitalism. Within this scenario, gay men began to be “represented as the epitome of an urban, metropolitan, consumerist lifestyle.”²⁵ This new stereotype of gay life served to celebrate a modern and progressive Ireland, positioned as a stark contrast to the early repressive and (p. 127) church-dominated version of the nation. Male homosexuality had only been legalized in 1993, and the most vociferous opponents against such legalization had been clerical and lay activists in the Irish Catholic church.²⁶

Expanding on Cronin’s analysis, Susannah Bowyer argues that, in Ireland and elsewhere, the modern icon of gay life relies on the identification and pursuit of pleasure, characteristic of consumer capitalism. “The libidinal overtones identified as significant in postmodern culture,” Bowyer explains, “coalesce in the global gay brand’s association with a covetable sense of sexual ease and enjoyment and the queer frisson of transgression.”²⁷ This liberal culture, “the global gay brand,” endorsed values of individualism that helped homosexuals reclaim their sexual freedom. Yet, in Celtic Tiger Ireland, homophobia remained prevalent. Many homosexuals continued to experience “marginalisation, harassment, violence and exclusion in education, work, and social life.”²⁸ Moreover, as Ridgway reminds us in his depiction of rent boy characters, the modern icon of gay life hardly represents the actual experiences of numerous Irish homosexuals—gay men who were non-white, older, rural, or lower-class, for example.

²³ Diarmaid Ferriter, *Occasions of Sin: Sex and Society in Modern Ireland* (London: Profile Books, 2009), 10.

²⁴ Peadar Kirby, *Celtic Tiger in Collapse: Explaining the Weaknesses of the Irish Model* (London: Palgrave MacMillan, 2010), 68.

²⁵ Michael G. Cronin, “‘He’s My Country’: Liberalism, Nationalism, and Sexuality in Contemporary Irish Gay Fiction,” *Éire-Ireland* 39, 3–4 (2004), 255.

²⁶ See, for example, *Lesbian and Gay Visions of Ireland: Towards the Twenty-First Century*, ed. Íde O’Carroll and Eoin Collins (London: Cassell, 1995).

²⁷ Susannah Bowyer, “Queer Patriots: Sexuality and the Character of National Identity in Ireland,” *Cultural Studies* 24, 6 (2010): 801–20

²⁸ Katherine O’Donnell, “Lesbian Lives and Studies in Ireland at the Fin de Siècle,” in *Tribades, Tommies and Transgressors. Histories of Sexualities: volume 1*, ed. Mary McAullifs and Sonja Tiernan (Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars, 2008), 3.

Ridgway's "Angelo" and *The Parts* deal with the failed relationships between a young gay man who is part of Dublin's gay scene, and a rent boy who remains trapped in a much more restricted and marginal world.

Ridgway explores gay life in contemporary Dublin, adopting an intersectional approach that challenges the celebratory modern icon of gay identity. Typically, John McCourt notes, Ridgway's characters "represent people drawn from a variety of mainstream social groups, ages, backgrounds and classes."²⁹ Apart from offering a social mosaic of Dublin, Ridgway's narratives are character-driven, and largely reflect the protagonists' consciousness. In this respect, McCourt rightly observes that

All of Ridgway's works share a common relative disinterest in external events and are less concerned with action, plot, and forward movement (although a dark, violent, everyday is ever present) than they are with a focus on individual thought processes, personal stasis, alienation, and, at times, collapse. . . . Ridgway's focus is far less on outer events than on the functioning and malfunctioning of the mind and with the mind's way of perceiving the world.³⁰

(p. 128) Ridgway not only describes the vulnerability and grim experiences of his rent boy characters, but, through this "malfunctioning of the mind" and failure to perceive other people's realities, also portrays the effects of the social silencing of male prostitution in contemporary Ireland.

Embedded in everyday language, silence—as Michel Foucault reminds us— is not an absence of communication, but "an element that functions alongside the things said," manifesting itself in "the thing one declines to say, or is forbidden to name, the discretion that is required between different speakers."³¹ Robin Patric Clair provides a further helpful conceptualization of the social uses of silence: "Silence and language create and re-create our social realities. From interpersonal relationships to the structuring of organizations, silent practices are pervasive and interwoven with linguistic practices.... The issues of power, politics, aesthetics, and economics are all part of the organizing of silence."³² In other words, people may exercise their freedom to speak or remain silent on certain issues, but silence manifests itself more forcefully when it informs individuals' assumptions, perceptions, and worldview. In the case of the media accounts on rent boys, in Ireland silence was "organized" in such a way that it fostered a lack of awareness of the unpalatable realities surrounding male prostitution. Placed outside the conventional channels of social interaction, literature can dissect the surreptitious ways in which dominant discourses employ strategies of silence to "organize" knowledge and power.

²⁹ John McCourt, "'All Stories Overlap': Reading Keith Ridgway's Short Fiction," *Journal of the Short Story in English* 63 (2014), 231.

³⁰ McCourt, 230.

³¹ Michael Foucault, *The History of Sexuality*, vol. 1 (1976; London: Penguin Books, 1998), 27.

³² Clair, 21.

Ridgway's "Angelo" and *The Parts* dramatize how the social silencing of prostitution operates at the level of interpersonal relationships.

In "Angelo," prostitution features as a subtext, a secret that the narrator— an unnamed young Dubliner who was Angelo's friend and lover—is unable to discover, despite the numerous clues he is given. Told in retrospect, the story revolves around the narrator's experiences with Angelo as he tries to come to terms with his sudden disappearance. Here, Ridgway creates an open universe for his gay characters, except for the mysterious Angelo, who acts and looks different than the others; he

did not fit the bill as a gay man really. His clothes were random, occasionally awful, he was lazy about his appearance so that it was not uncommon to see him turn up with greasy hair and unattractive stubble, and it annoyed me greatly that he could often be seen in places like The George or The Front Lounge, carrying an old plastic bag from Dunnes.³³

(p. 129) The narrator conforms to the modern image of a liberated, middle-class gay man who enjoys being part of Dublin's commercial gay scene, yet Angelo is cast as an outsider even if he is also gay. Ridgway's economic metaphor—"to fit the bill"—brilliantly captures the idea that, to be regarded as a standard gay man, one should care about his physical attractiveness and be, or at least look like, a middle-class consumer. As a representative of Dublin's modern culture, the narrator reaffirms this confluence between consumerism and gay identity when he remarks that Angelo "did not wear aftershave, did not belong to a gym, did not go to the theatre or the cinema or seem to do anything that involved any kind of expenditure at all" (A 210). The narrator and Angelo live in the same city, but they belong to two different worlds. Influenced by mainstream discourses that silence the realities of the socially oppressed, the narrator cannot "see" Angelo beyond the values and conventions of his own social class.

Throughout the story, gay sex is described in the language of consumerism. In this way, Ridgway shows how this new liberal culture of sexual freedom can heighten the negative aspects of individualism and sexual commodification. The narrator's sexual fascination with Angelo—his fetishization of the exotic foreigner—prevents him from developing a more profound relationship with his lover: "I enjoyed him, and it was enjoyment without clutter, without notions of permanence or exclusivity or special treatment" (A 208). The typical rules of romance are disregarded here, and, despite Angelo's wishes to become partners, the narrator insists: "I'm your friend and occasional shag" (A 206). Frustrated, Angelo accuses the narrator and his other gay friends of practicing "McDonald's sex" (A 217). Ridgway may be somewhat sarcastic when he describes the narrator's "fast-food" approach to sex, but the metaphor tellingly connotes that this model of gay life is an import from a gay male global culture. Confused by

³³ Keith Ridgway, "Angelo," *Standard Time* (London: Faber and Faber, 2001), 201; hereafter cited parenthetically thus: (A 201).

Angelo's attentions after their first sexual encounter, the narrator remarks, "It was right to exchange blow jobs but pleasantries like this were something of an invasion" (A 198). The morally ambiguous narrator shows no real concern when, as they have sex, he realizes that Angelo "had a scar, horribly pinkish white, on his lower back, ending in his left buttock, which he claimed was from a stabbing in London, which was one of those version stories, it changed over time" (A 196). Along the narrative, Ridgway offers clues indicating that Angelo is vulnerable and that he is involved in some kind of dark underworld—but the narrator continually fails to read the signs. He demonstrates very little interest in getting to know Angelo beyond their sexual connection.

To dramatize the two characters' social differences, Ridgway contrasts the narrator's misperceptions and prejudices with Angelo's evasions and distortions of his actual experiences. As the story continues, we learn that Angelo made up stories about his past, remained silent about his personal life, and that none of his friends knew where he lived. Additionally, because the reader is deliberately (p. 130) left unsure as to the extent of the narrator's self-deception, Ridgway effectively captures the ambiguities between knowing and unknowing, between innocence and willful blindness. After some months together, the narrator is already aware that Angelo has a double life: "I do remember thinking, maybe for the first time, about the oddness of Angelo's name. Angelo. What the hell kind of a name is that?" (A 218). He also informs us that Angelo often ran out of money and then disappeared without explanation, just to return some days later and take him out "for wildly expensive meals" (A 210). Despite these strange circumstances, the narrator suspects nothing when an unknown, older man phones him to ask about Angelo, with a "posh, wealthy, clear, business-like" voice (A 218). When the narrator informs him about the call, a frightened and awkward Angelo realizes that Mr. Duncan—a rich man who had taken him under his wing—has reappeared to claim him back. "Stuttering" and "shame faced" (A 225), a terrified Angelo struggles to communicate the story without being explicit about the fact that Mr. Duncan was either his client or pimp. Though he senses his distress, the narrator simply assumes that Angelo is embarrassed because he is "being tracked down by a jealous former sugar daddy who wants him back" (A 224). Shortly after this, Angelo disappears without trace. The narrator, who had dismissed the real danger his friend was facing, now regrets his past actions: "I'm stuck here, stuck with the memory of him... Gone. Disappeared. And here I am rattling away" (A 248). Significantly, even though prostitution features as a silenced reality, a subtext of sexual exploitation explains the enigmatic ending of Ridgway's short story.

"Angelo" depicts the coalescence of different types of silences. On the one hand, Angelo's inability to talk about his situation bespeaks a culture of stigma concerning sexual work. His silence reminds us of the fact that, in Ireland and elsewhere, "male prostitution . . . has long been a highly stigmatized activity— because it is often illegal and

widely considered shameful.”³⁴ On the other, the narrator’s attitude—his ignorance, incredulity, and middle-class complacency—also seems to be a consequence of the social silencing of male prostitution. In the end, Ridgway’s story leaves readers wondering if Angelo could have been saved had the protagonists managed to break their walls of silence.

In *The Parts*, unlike the somewhat indirect handling of prostitution in “Angelo,” Ridgway deals with the topic in a straightforward, even “in-your-face” manner. Published in the most liberal and triumphant years of Celtic Tiger Ireland, *The Parts* foregrounds the alienation and social divides of the early 2000s Dublin. Ridgway’s is a complex and original portrayal of Dublin, one that “strongly convey[s] the idea of multiple cities existing in the same space (p. 131) at the same time.”³⁵ To reinforce this notion of coexisting “multiple cities,” the novel employs such techniques as polyphony, fragmentation, shifting perspectives, and a pastiche of narrative styles (third-person omniscient, third-person subjective, first-person and stream of consciousness), and widely varying forms of texts, among them letters and e-mails, chat room conversations, Dublin listings and event guides, and male escort advertisements. In his insightful review, Derek Hand comments that the novel is “mindful of its own status as a text.” For Hand, this “acknowledgement of form indicates the difficulty that exists in the telling. Thus, the characters’ struggle to project themselves in the stories they create becomes the author’s own as he searches for a form appropriate to the story he is attempting to relate.”³⁶

Moreover, the novel’s multilayered form undermines cultural hierarchies that organize knowledge and promote silence on certain realities of abuse, like poverty and sexual exploitation. In *The Parts*, Ridgway portrays the silenced reality of prostitution (and the social fragmentation it implies) in various ways: for example, one of the characters expresses his surprise when discovering the rent boy trade in the Phoenix Park: “Who could tell that this was going on, right here, just here, right in the middle of town. . . . It’s like one city inside another. Parallel cities.”³⁷ To represent silence and the limits of knowledge, Ridgway also employs such discursive strategies as pauses in speech, fragmented utterances, linguistic estrangement, evasions and distortions, gaps and omissions.

As a polyphonic novel, *The Parts* contains a cast of six main characters and numerous short sections focusing alternatively on each of them. The characters’ story lines become connected by the seventeen-year-old Kevin, or “Kez,” who traverses the diverse social spheres of Dublin life in his work as a rent boy, emerging as “the moral

³⁴ Jeffrey Escoffier, “Sex Work and Prostitution,” GLBTQ online Encyclopedia, 2005. http://www.glbtaarchive.com/ssh/sex_work_male_S.pdf.

³⁵ Anthea Lawson, “In Dublin’s Unfair City,” *Guardian*, 9 March 2003.

³⁶ Derek Hand, “Dislocated in Dublin,” *Irish Times*, 18 January 2003.

³⁷ Keith Ridgway, *The Parts* (London: Faber and Faber, 2003), 367; hereafter cited parenthetically thus: (TP 367).

centre on which the novel turns.”³⁸ The first moment readers see Kevin is from the defamiliarizing perspective of Kitty Flood, who lives in a rich Dublin district. This passage illustrates what Emilie Pine has called “agnosia,” a medical term she adapts for her analyses of contemporary Ireland, which refers to a “cognitive inability to recognise or understand the significance of what is being seen.”³⁹ Pine quotes from the 2009 Ryan Report to argue that a form of “social agnosia” helped maintain the historical silencing of child abuse in Ireland, because “the general public (p. 132) was often uninformed and usually uninterested. All these pools of unknowing reinforced each other.”⁴⁰

In Ridgway’s novel, while looking through her bedroom window, Kitty spots a naked boy in a neighbor’s house and observes how an older man reaches for him, his hands moving the boy, “straightening him out, tilting his head back, opening his mouth”—then the older man “clamps his own mouth over the boy’s” (TP 9). As they have sex, the boy “turns his head away and makes a face and looks as if he was on his way out of the world” (TP 10). Confused, Kitty is unable to comprehend what is really happening: “It goes on too long. It’s impossible to believe, and if Kitty is seeing this then she’s probably laughing” (TP 10). Kitty’s agnosia originates from the social silencing of the underworld of prostitution.

Arguably, through Kitty’s incredulous gaze, Ridgway also depicts a kind of indifference to, or nonrecognition of, class oppression and sexual exploitation. In her study of female prostitution, Catherine McGurran has identified a post-feminist discourse in Celtic Tiger Ireland, which suggests that the “selling of sex has become accepted by society,” and that prostitution “is now an industry based on choice.”⁴¹ Far from endorsing this liberal view on prostitution, Ridgway’s *The Parts* looks instead at the darkest aspects of Kevin’s life as a rent boy. Like most real-life rent boys, Ridgway’s character hails from a dysfunctional family and an economically disadvantaged background. Kevin’s single mother, for instance, is unemployed and suffers from extreme depression. The mother, Kevin suspects, knows that he is involved in prostitution, but the shame and pain about it impede an honest but hurtful conversation between the two: “She never asked him what exactly it was that he did. If she had to talk about it she pretended confusion. . . . She knew what he did . . . she knew” (TP 155). Silence, here, is used as a self-protective strategy, as “the discretion that is required between speakers.”⁴² Kevin’s other family member is Vincent, his older half-brother, a criminal who also happens to be his pimp, and who continually exhorts him to increase his clientele: “You’ll be getting a call this week, so

³⁸ O’Donnell, 191.

³⁹ Emilie Pine, “Commemorating Abuse: Gender Politics and Making Space,” UCD Scholarcast, 2013, 6. Available at <http://www.ucd.ie/scholarcast/scholarcast34.html>.

⁴⁰ Pine, 6.

⁴¹ Catherine McGurran, “‘Damning Men’s Souls’: The Evolution of Irish Prostitution Memoirs,” *Études Irlandaises* 39, 1 (2014), 83.

⁴² Foucault, 27.

check your fucking messages right? Cos you never do” (TP 157). Exploited by his brutal brother, Kevin finds it impossible to escape from prostitution.

In *The Parts*, Ridgway inserts short sections reporting Kevin’s emotional problems, which result from his vulnerability and sexual objectification: “He thought his best feature was probably his shoulders, but no one ever paid them much attention” (TP 73). In these stream-of-consciousness sections, readers (**p. 133**) have access to Kevin’s unspoken fears, like his idea that “someone would take him to the country and cut his throat” (TP 68). Kevin, who lives in a permanent state of anxiety, has the uneasy feeling that the money he earns “cut[s] into him” (TP 35). Written in a different typeface, Kevin’s sections often interrupt the other characters’ storylines, reminding readers of his presence at times when he is absent. Unlike public discourses that establish a hierarchy of knowledge that silences the experiences of rent boys, Ridgway elevates Kevin’s perspective to a superior status. He features as the wisest, most profound character in the novel—the only one who, at a time of rampant individualism, expresses emotions of self-transcendence: “Kez always knew, always, that whenever he was with one of these men he was also, and he liked this, with the city, that he peeled off another layer, revealed something more of it” (TP 109).

One of the dark aspects that Ridgway tackles in *The Parts* is the constant danger rent boys confront, as many of their clients seek to fulfill their ephebophilic fantasies of domination and subjugation of younger males. McGrath’s documentary illustrates that sexual violence is a common occurrence in the lives of rent boys, who explain that “[punters] have this thing about power, that gives them a certain amount of enjoyment. . . . Most of the guys are into violence; they are older than you, they dictate you.”⁴³ At work, Kevin’s main worry is that clients cross the line between consensual sex and abuse. In one episode, he considers escaping from a “dangerously horny” punter (TP 111), who “kept on squeezing [his] thigh in a way that actually hurt” (TP 110). Ridgway’s character was also beaten up by one of his clients, a memory that haunts him: “Sometimes still he thought that his jaw hurt. It ached, like it was remembering. Then he would console himself with what it was he had learned from the whole Chester Haft disaster” (TP 139). Taking advantage of the underground nature of prostitution, Chester Haft exercised his tyranny upon a defenseless, lower-class rent boy. Unsurprisingly, the attack went unreported, because Kevin would have needed to admit his involvement in prostitution. But, more important, he is also convinced that nobody would help him:

He told nobody. It would be a hard thing to tell—it would bring questions and long looks, and maybe it would make people laugh and they would talk about him as if he wasn’t there. People would look at him differently, as someone they probably shouldn’t trust too far, as someone who might not be there too long. It would make him transparent and temporary to others. (TP 140)

⁴³ McGrath, *Boys for Rent*

Ridgway recognizes, and denounces here, the reality that where there is social silence about a specific type of abuse, the victims—if they choose to speak out— may encounter other people’s disbelief, incomprehension, and harsh judgment. (p. 134) Like Angelo’s silence in the short story, Kevin’s own inability to speak on his life experiences also carries strong implications regarding the shame and stigma of prostitution. In Ireland, the mainstream discourses on male prostitution have focused on clients and on moral issues; Ridgway instead concentrates on the rent boy’s experiences and emotional world, undermining the silencing of the gruesome realities surrounding prostitution.

The Parts also features a man in his early twenties, Barry, who is part of Dublin’s gay youth culture. Unlike the narrator in “Angelo,” Barry is frustrated about his contemporary gay culture, which, for example, promotes alternative sexual and gender roles as something natural and desirable. In a gay club amusingly called “Penetration,” Barry is rejected by a potential lover, who asked him whether he was a “top” or “bottom”: “What a stupid bloody question anyway— *are you active or passive, do you take it or give it, are you this or that?* The cheek of him, asking that, reducing everyone to that, as if it was set in stone, as if all that mattered was which one you were, fucker or fucked” (TP 44). Barry protests against this “conceivably heterosexual view of sex” (TP 44), a sexual conduct that has gained immense popularity in the post-liberation male gay culture: “Whereas in gay liberation the answer to roles was to ‘shed’ them, in later decades they were picked up, polished and redeployed for the purposes of sexual excitement.”⁴⁴ Ridgway’s novel accurately reflects a situation which has only exacerbated in recent years, due to the increasing dominance of a digital culture that, as Kay Siebler explains, reduces gay identity to an index of sexual behaviors and body types (e.g., in dating websites and mobile phone applications). Today’s queer culture thus reinforces “binaries of sex, sexuality, and gender,”⁴⁵ creating “archetypes” that have a strong influence on the identity formation of gay men.⁴⁶ As David Halperin had already warned in the early 2000s, “post-liberation gay male culture . . . has tended to make sexuality, not love, the lynchpin of gay identity.”⁴⁷ The negative effects of such culture can be perceived in Ridgway’s character; Barry has numerous sexual partners, nonetheless he feels “unloved, loveless” (TP 119). When he goes on a date with another man, the two of them complain about “the gay scene” (TP 214), but they end up having sex the same day, never to see each other again. As in “Angelo,” in *The Parts* Ridgway exposes how this sexual lifestyle creates serious obstacles to intermale intimacy and private love.

Related to the sexual lifestyle above described is the failed romantic story between Kevin and Barry. Barry—who works for Joe, a Dublin journalist— wanders up and down the quays one night, looking for rent boys to interview (p. 135) When Barry meets Kevin,

⁴⁴ Sheila Jeffreys, *Unpacking Queer Politics* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2003), 13.

⁴⁵ Kay Siebler, *Learning Queer Identity in the Digital Age* (London: Palgrave, 2017), 80.

⁴⁶ Siebler, 99.

⁴⁷ David Halperin, “Pal O’ Me Heart,” *London Review of Books*, May 22, 2003.

he develops a sexual but paternalistic interest in him, romanticizing himself as the boy's possible savior. Their only date is described from Barry's perspective, and here Ridgway humorously portrays this character's shortcomings, of which he becomes aware: "His idiotic subconscious, trained as it was by pop culture psychology, . . . had decided to go *in loco parentis* to the object of his desire. It was an arse ways Oedipus, horrid to behold" (TP 298). Given their insecurities on what can be spoken, their interactions are characterized by numerous interruptions, reformulations, evasions and silences. As they have dinner, they find themselves in pleasant company, but the romanticism is broken the moment Kevin announces he must leave:

'I have to go'

'Where?'

Kevin frowned, and seemed to hunt around for an answer

'Oh,' said Barry, 'I mean, really? So early? That's a pity?'

...

He found it suddenly appalling

'Do you have to?' he asked

'Go? Yeah, sorry'

No, he tried to say, I mean do you have to fuck for money? But he nodded and stuck his finger in the dregs of his espresso. (TP 303)

Communicated through indirection and silent gestures, their distinct sensibilities incapacitate them to bridge the gap created by their social class differences, provoking "the first uneasy silence of the evening" (TP 303). Kevin cannot bring himself to mention the reason for his sudden departure; he has to go and meet a punter, an encounter he cannot miss because it was organized by his brother. On his part, Barry sulks and feels that he has failed in his romantic and sexual pretensions. Even though he presumably accepts what his friend does for a living, Barry fails to see beyond the social silencing of the lives of boys like Kevin, for whom prostitution is not a simple matter of choice. Frustrated, Barry reverts to his usual fast-food sex life and goes to the gay sauna to "chase ass" (TP 318). Ridgway does not openly criticize this sexual lifestyle, but he shows how it damages personal relationships; Kevin, kidnapped by his client, phones his friend for help, but Barry was busy having sex with strangers.⁴⁸

In his attempt to find Kevin, Barry returns with Joe to the quays to ask about his whereabouts. Rent boys, who do not know one another by their real names, react with suspicion, unable to believe that Barry is no cop, pimp, or punter. When Barry insists on asking about Kevin, one of the rent boys mocks him: "Aw. Have you brought him a vest?" (TP 374). Barry then complains:

It breaks one of the rules of social intercourse, forgive me, between these guys and us.

The system does not allow for it. For you turning up and being concerned for the

⁴⁸ Kevin is used as a guinea pig for a potent drug one of the main characters, a corrupt doctor, is testing. Kevin eventually saves himself and decides to escape from Dublin

health and safety of one of their number. They are rattled. They are regrouping. They don't know what to make of it. (TP 377)

Interestingly, Ridgway presents us here with a reverse case of agnosia. The social silencing of abuse provokes the disbelief of those who do not suffer it, but those who do suffer such abuse, like rent boys, may internalize the dynamics of oppression and thus react with the same disbelief when the “rules of social intercourse” are broken. Ridgway produces in *The Parts* a narrative where the social silencing of prostitution is both dramatized and undermined through his characters’ agnosia or, in McCourt’s words, “the malfunctioning of the mind.”⁴⁹ Throughout the novel, Ridgway exposes the ways in which the various cultural practices of silence—which organize knowledge as much as language does— connect with issues of power, politics and social class, maintaining the cycles of oppression afflicting rent boys.

In “Angelo” and *The Parts*, Ridgway vividly portrays the glitter and grime of the materialistic Dublin of the Celtic Tiger years. Both texts abound with references to a new liberal culture of sexual freedom, individualism, and consumerism. However, the rent boy characters, because they belong to a lower social stratum, remain trapped in a marginal and restricted world. Ridgway foregrounds this clash of cultures in his depiction of failed relationships between a male prostitute and young gay man, whose agnosia, middle-class complacency, and prejudices originate from social silencing of the gruesome conditions surrounding prostitution. By so doing, Ridgway also challenges the celebratory modern icon of gay life, exposing the ways it contributes to the negative outcome of these homosexual relationships. This last aspect is, perhaps, more salient in the short story, where the narrator cannot “see” Angelo beyond his own social class values and conventions. In *The Parts*, Ridgway offers readers an unflinching portrayal of the realities of Dublin male street prostitutes. Through Kevin’s tribulations and vulnerability, readers not only witness the ugly side of Dublin life, but are also encouraged to grow their awareness of the social class oppression, exploitation, and marginalization of the “dispossessed” in the supposedly prosperous Celtic Tiger Ireland. Ridgway tackles the social agnosia concerning male prostitution, addressing what the Ryan Report called “the pools of unknowing” that made the public “uninformed and usually uninterested” about the existence of abuse.⁵⁰

In the years of the writing and publication of Ridgway’s “Angelo” and *The Parts*, there was very little public attention in Ireland regarding rent boys; what (p. 137) little discussion there was showed no concern about the destitution these youngsters suffered. Common reactions in Irish society were to express a desire to keep prostitution out of sight, or to show a moralistic concern over the double lives that many self-identified heterosexual men led. This concern over the “true,” but repressed, sexual identity of

⁴⁹ McCourt, 230.

⁵⁰ Pine, 6.

clients was completely of a piece with the social discourse of Celtic Tiger Ireland, which stressed personal and sexual liberation from the shackles of “old” Catholic and conservative Ireland. This new liberal culture, though, still obscured the grim realities of poverty, exploitation, and economic disparity. In his fiction, Ridgway adopts a much more humane and comprehensive approach to this matter, disturbing the complacency of a liberal, middle-class Ireland that silences the often painful experiences of rent boys.